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Battery Cell
Assembly Twin

D4.1: Data landscape and infrastructure related requirements

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Abstract:	<i>This document summarizes the results of BatCAT tasks T4.1 and T4.3. Its main contributions are: an analysis and prioritization of concrete optimization problems to be addressed by the project, a list of user stories formulating requirements for the various architecture components, and a set of competency questions that will serve as input for the ontology development. All the information was gathered via interviews, questionnaires, collaborative workshops and inter-work package exchanges.</i>
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Abbreviations and acronyms

API	Application Programming Interface
ASP	Answer Set Programming
CQ	Competency Question
EQ	Example Query
DFT	Density Functional Theory
DKMS	Data and Knowledge Management Software
DoE	Design of Experiment
DoS	Design of Simulation
DT	Digital Twin
ELN	Electronic Lab Notebook
ERP	Enterprise Resource Planning
KB	Knowledge Base
KO	Key Objective
ID	Identifier
LIB	Lithium-Ion Battery
MCO	Multi-Criteria Optimisation
MC	Monte Carlo (method)
MD	Molecular Dynamics
NIB	Sodium-Ion Battery
OWL	Web Ontology Language
P2D / P3D	Pseudo two dimensional (model) / Pseudo three dimensional (model)
RFB	Redox Flow Battery
SEM	Scanning electron microscopy
TBD	To be defined
US	User Story
XPS	X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy

Note: For abbreviations related to the BatCAT architecture components see Table 3. In general, abbreviations used as part of identifier tags in tables of the Appendix are defined in the respective sections.

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1. Executive summary

One of the key aspects of scientific collaboration is exchange of research data and knowledge, their representation and re-usability. Understanding the way BatCAT partners currently handle the research data and knowledge within already established research facilities and understanding their requirements for the project use cases is a necessary step before building the BatCAT data and knowledge management infrastructure.

This document addresses the first challenges related to KO4 (*Provide a knowledge base to support battery cell manufacturing across processes and partners through a federated, integrated, and semantically enriched data space*), namely building the data and metadata landscape (T4.3) and gathering user requirements (T4.1). It summarizes the methodology designed to address them in BatCAT and draws conclusion on their future impact on knowledge infrastructure related tasks of WP4 (T4.2 - Knowledge base for cell manufacturing, T4.4 - Metadata standardization) and WP5 (e.g., T5.2 - *Multicriteria optimization* and T5.4 - *Human-digital interaction*).

The structure of the document is as follows: In [Sec. 2](#) we summarize the methodology used, especially for interviews, the optimization questionnaire, user stories and competency questions. Then we give in [Sec. 3](#) a high-level summary of the results of the data and metadata landscape questionnaire, with answers grouped into simulation, experimental and manufacturing data. Next [Sec. 4](#) gives an analysis of the requirements gathered from the interviews and the optimization questionnaire. The conclusions are drawn in [Sec. 5](#). In the appendix, the questions we asked are listed (see [Appendix A](#) for optimization, and [Appendix B](#) for the data landscape). Then, the formulation of requirements in terms of epics and user stories is given in [Appendix C](#), and as competency questions in [Appendix D](#). Finally, [Appendix E](#) lists characterization techniques and instruments that will be used within BatCAT. We note that naturally there is some overlap in content between the various formulations of requirements, as the domain described and the overall input material used is the same. However, we believe different formulations offer different perspectives and are valuable as each of them is most suited as input for the following project tasks.

2. Methodology

Interviews

As a first step, we defined a set of 9 personas (*roles*), including: *Manufacturing use-case owner* (internal), *Experimentalist* (internal or external), *Simulation researcher* (internal), *Digital twin technology user* (internal), *Developer of a related platform* (external), *Policy expert* (external), *Customer* (external) and *IT Administrator* (internal), cf. [Appendix C](#)³. Then, we identified people that could represent each role and carried out two-stage interviews. Overall, 10 experts were interviewed at least once, and most of them interviewed twice, with each slot lasting 30 minutes, the second slot going more in depth on the topics. As preparatory material, the interviewees were sent various sets of questions, including those in [Appendix B](#), and a questionnaire used by partner IndiScale (IS) for onboarding of users on CaosDB (that will be the core component of the BatCAT data and knowledge management system). We note that the interviews were carried out in close coordination with

³ With internal/external we mean with respect to BatCAT, i.e., whether they work on not on the BatCAT project.

T6.1 - *Industrial and use-case requirements analysis* and T7.2 - *Citizens' role and societal and gender dimensions*.

Knowledge base optimization questionnaire

We created a questionnaire as a webform, see [Appendix A](#) for snapshots of all its parts. The questionnaire begins with definitions of the proposed optimization problems. Participants then voted on different types of optimization issues, including logic-based, MCO-based, on-chip hybrid problems, and the necessary machine learning-based prediction problems. In total, 19 respondents completed the questionnaire. Figure 2.1 shows how the participants were divided into external and internal. Figure 2.2 shows the distribution of participants in terms of the roles defined in the previous subsection.

Figure 2.1 The percentage of participants categorized as internal and external.

Figure 2.2 The Percentage of Participants Categorized by “role” (omitting the distinction internal/external)

Requirements formulated as user stories and competency questions

User stories and competency questions are standard ways to formulate requirements from the user perspective: the first ones are generally used for software engineering⁴, the second one are typical of knowledge engineering (e.g., as part of ontology engineering process). In this section, we briefly describe what they are, how we gathered them, give some examples and outline how they will be used in the rest of the project.

User stories and epics are both formulated as:

“As <role>, I intend to do <concretely described action> in order to progress toward <overarching objective>.”

The difference between the two types is that epics are more general: their action is the objective of multiple user stories, their objective a wider one. Given this structure, we collect the three variable parts (role, concrete

⁴ M. Cohn, “*User Stories Applied: For Agile Software Development*”, United Kingdom, Pearson Education, 2004.

action and overarching objective) in a table. Additionally, we identify what architecture component the user story is mostly relevant for and assign priorities following the MOSCOW types (i.e.: Must, Should, Could, Won't). An example of a user story is:

“As an experimentalist internal to BatCAT, I intend to Record all processes undergone by a sample, including artificial/accelerated ageing in order to progress toward track(ing) the whole history (across laboratories) of each experimental sample being characterized in BatCAT”. This falls under the epic: “As an experimentalist internal to BatCAT, I intend to Track the whole history (across laboratories) of each experimental sample being characterized in BatCAT in order to progress toward [g]athering complete experimental data on batteries”, cf. user story US_KBP_EI_1 and epic EP_EI_1 in Table 2. The unique ID tag of the user story reflects the type, target architecture component and role. Similarly for epics, except that they don't have the architecture component part, since they can refer to multiple components. See Table 3. List of architecture components, abbreviation and main responsible WP in [Appendix C](#) for more details.

Based on the LOT methodology⁵ for ontology engineering, we also gather requirements in the form of Competency Questions (CQs) and Facts. Competency Questions (CQs) are questions that an ontology (for a certain domain) must be able to answer. "Facts" are sentences capturing key relations of the domain. They are used as an alternative to CQs and can be easier than CQs for users who are not familiar with ontology engineering. We assign them a unique identifier and tag them based on the area they mostly concern, cf. Table 4 in [Appendix D](#). An example of a cross-area CQ is: “What are the main properties of the electrolyte?”, whose answer is “Composition (salts, solvents), purity, transport properties (viscosity, ionic conductivity), density”. An example of a “fact” for the simulation area is: “Surrogate models can be classified by the dimensionality of input and output fed to the neural network” (cf. CQ_CRO_1 and FA_SIM_1 in [Appendix D](#)).

Internally, for both USs and CQs, we also gather other information on provenance and versioning, not displayed in this document, but available to consortial partners.

USs and CQs were either formulated directly by the users during interactive workshops, or by WP4 partners based on the gathered material, cross-work-package collaboration and discussions.

The user stories will be used by other BatCAT tasks as initial requirements, and a mapping of components to work packages will facilitate the split of responsibilities, cf. Table 3 in [Appendix C](#). The CQs will be the starting point of work in BatCAT T4.4 - “Metadata standardization”.

3. Data and metadata landscape

We have collected answers from the consortium partners to a set of questions (cf. [Appendix B](#)), and provide below a high-level summary organized in three groups: simulation, experimental and manufacturing data. Each summary gives an overview of the status quo at a few partner institutions (three or more in each group). We note that the last two questions of the set are not addressed in these summaries as optimization and example queries are treated separately (cf. [Sec 4](#) and Table 6 in [Appendix D](#)). We close the section with a graphical overview of the current storage and the envisaged one in BatCAT.

Analysis of the answers: simulation data

⁵ M. Poveda Villalón, A. Fernández Izquierdo, et al., "LOT: An industrial oriented ontology engineering framework," *Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence* 111: 104755, doi:10.1016/j.engappai.2022.104755, 2022.

Data in a nutshell

In BatCAT, the wide array of simulation tools and techniques has the capacity to produce a wide array of data, based on the goals and scales of the simulations.

In general, the simulations provide: simulated time series of global/system-wide quantities, or spatiotemporal fields from which we can ascertain forces, stresses, displacements, velocities, pressure, charges, health state, and concentrations; simulated physical properties/parameters, such as diffusivity, viscosity.

General information

Each institution has in-house rules or regulations regarding storage and long-term maintenance of data storage. In general, data is kept as long as needed for individual projects or longer as dictated by funding mandates. Most data are stored as openly available / open source.

Data type is described above, comprising mainly: 1) Time series and 2) Simulated physical properties

Data generation

The data is typically generated as simulation outputs, with the simulation initiated by a user that is typically a scientist or engineer. The data needed as input includes data coming from experiments or molecular simulations, such as material parameters; the outputs are as described above. All data is event-based (i.e., generated by a single or multiple simulations).

Data structure

Data is a combination of human readable files (ascii text, csv) and binary files. The binary formats are a combination of open-source ones, e.g., NetCDF and some proprietary binary formats from commercial computational software.

Metadata

Metadata are of several types: Related to input and outputs (i.e., both existing and produced data), e.g., column names, with physical units given in column headers.

The keywords and structure vary for each organization and may require some harmonization (formats used mostly). Standards and ontologies are not used by most simulation partners.

Terminology sources

Terminology used come from past experience and know-how (literature, books, habits...). As there are many past collaborations, it is rather well shared around the world.

Data access

The data supplier and owner are the scientists in charge of the simulations in the name of the institution they represent. The access rights are generally open source.

Data quality

Data quality can be validated thanks to:

- Experience of the operator who checks the obtained outputs
- Quality assurance and control of the simulation software
- Numerical analysis and the input data quality (either from experiment or simulations)

No major issues of this type of data are reported in the answers.

Analysis of the answers: experimental data

Data in a nutshell

Experimentalists provide:

- Experimental data as time series from which specific information can be extracted (capacity, diffusion coefficients, capacity loss, resistance, etc.)
 - o Converted from raw data as Excel files or CSV file. Header is either defined during post treatment (CPI, IFPEN) or as it comes from the device (NIC)
- Experimental data as values (quantity measured, experimental observation): images, slurry viscosity, coating resistance, etc.
 - o Word report generated by an operator

General information

There are no ground rules regarding data storage using either hard drives or in-house storage systems but it is kept as long as necessary (minimum the time of the project).

Data type is described above:

- Time series
- Experimentally measured properties
- Images
- Observations
- Provider information (on the material)

Data generation

Data is generated by human operators who work on test benches or experiments based on files generated by the device, its software, or measured parameters.

Data is an input and output of software (input current or voltage from potentiostat), output measured voltage, measured temperature, etc.

All data is event-based (generated by an experiment or a measurement).

Data structure

Data is generally generated as human readable files (word, csv) and documented internally. They are not open-source.

Metadata

Metadata are of several types:

- Related to produced data, e.g., column names, with units given in column headers (IFPEN, CPI, NIC), or using device generated data (EC-lab for instance) providing metadata in file headers
- Using the data storage systems providing test metadata stored in the database (IFPEN) or in a data tracker (CPI)
- The keywords and structure are defined internally to each organisation, and will require harmonization (Voltage vs Ecell vs Tension; English vs French labels, etc.)
- Standards and ontologies are not used yet

Terminology sources

Terminology used come from past experience and know-how (literature, books, habits...). As there are many past collaborations, it is rather well shared around the world.

Data access

The data provider is the scientist in charge of the experiment (CPI, NIC, IFPEN) in the name of the company. The data owner is the scientist and so the partner. The access rights are not clear so far, this needs to be better defined in the course of the project, in line with the consortium agreement and grant agreement.

Data quality

Data quality can be validated thanks to:

- Experience of the operator who checks the obtained outputs (IFPEN, NIC)
- Quality insurance procedures, e.g., regular calibration checks (IFPEN)
- Repeatability tests with automated treatment (CPI)

Main issues reported are:

- Cell failure due to manufacturing issues
- Test failure due to external problems
- Metadata missing due to old tests where such data were not recorded

Analysis of the answers: manufacturing/use-case data

The three partners generating manufacturing/use-case data (CPI, VANEVO, and BIREX) each have distinct approaches to managing manufacturing data, reflecting their unique operational needs and technological capabilities.

Data in a nutshell

- CPI: Experimental data is obtained from software (electrochemical) using in-house developed methods. Data is converted to Excel or CSV format. Observational data is based on experiments in the laboratory. This includes qualitative data recorded in Word documents, and quantitative data recorded in an Excel file (data tracker), requiring manual human input rather than automated population of a table. Uses Biovia Notebook for comprehensive data management, emphasizing translational (that is, applied) research.
- VANEVO: Material properties, manufacturing data, experimental/characterization data. Uses Excel sheets and OneNote tables, transitioning to an ERP (Enterprise Resource Planning) system for better data management.
- BIREX: Focus on wireless communication and data exchange for manufacturing.

General information

CPI: Electrochemical characterization, materials characterization (formulation/manufacturing data), experimental observations. Data is stored in an internal data tracker (Excel file). Data is stored for the duration of a project, then archived, never deleted.

VANEVO: Manufacturing/sensor/monitoring/design data. No database yet, data is typically stored for 5 years.

Data Generation

- CPI: Data generated from pilot line operations, testing facilities, and applied research projects. Data is event-based and produced by software (in relation to devices) or human (observations).

- VANEVO: Data is generated by operating battery systems, test benches (operated by human), experiments conducted by researchers. Data is typically output of a battery management system. It is generated both regularly and event-based (operation data and event data, such as malfunctions)
- BIREX: Data generated from temperature and pressure sensors, thermal cameras, and manufacturing equipment, like milling and mixing machines.

Data structure

CPI: All data formats are human readable (H), not open-source (No), and documented (Yes).

VANEVO: All data formats are human readable (H), not open-source (No), and documented (Yes, internally).

BIREX: Uses JSON for data exchange, dependent on device specifications.

Metadata

Metadata in column headers. In-house metadata schema, possibly customer dependent. No ontology or ISO-like standards.

Terminology Sources

The terminology is sector-specific, widely used in industry and in scientific literature worldwide. The terminology is not always consistent across projects yet. In some cases, terminology harmonization is provided by the data management software used (e.g., battery specific data management software). However, this is not done in more general data management software like Biovia Notebook.

Data access

Data is restricted access to the company and their customer (where relevant).

Data quality

At CPI, data is assessed for quality (reproducibility of cells is tested). This is carried out through exporting the data into a statistical modelling software which will flag anomalies. If working on Excel, the experimentalist will interpret the data themselves. Typical issues with testing that can affect the quality of data are cell specific and they arise due to issues associated with the manufacturing process, or the materials used.

At VANEVO, over time the metadata schema is growing, so this has to be taken into account for data across long periods of time.

Overview of current and future data storage and access

Below, in Figure 3.1, we summarize graphically the data storage and access, as they are now at the partners institutions and as they will be within the planned BatCAT data infrastructure. The current situation is characterized by a heterogeneous and distributed structure. Data is being collected, processed, and stored on

1. Personal laptops, tablet, and desktop computers with built-in or removable storage devices.
2. Multi-user workstations (e.g. a desktop computer in a lab) with built-in or removable storage devices.
3. Shared file storages and other storage services (e.g. electronic lab notebook, cloud storage, network filesystem, database management systems)

Some Devices and system are stationary and highly available on a local network, a virtual private network, or the internet. Other devices are non-stationary and at least temporary offline. Data is being stored with personal access only or group-readable, and shared using dedicated services or peer-to-peer exchange of removable storage devices.

The planned architecture needs to reduce the complexity of the infrastructure and the heterogeneity by placing a common gateway for data access and sharing while preserving the control over the access for the data providers. The next section expands on the broader architecture of the BatCAT digital twin.

Figure 3.1 Overview of data storage and access currently (left) and planned one with BatCAT (right). The complexity of the infrastructure at each site is encapsuled and hidden behind a common gateway, the Peripheral KB Node.

4. Knowledge Base Infrastructure Requirements

Architecture components

The BatCAT overall architecture is summarized in the figure below.

Figure 4.1 Overview architecture of BatCAT: components and relations between them

The components are: Decision support system [incl. DoE+DoS] (DSS); Knowledge base – central (KBC); Knowledge base – peripheral (KBP); Real-time environment [incl. actionable models] (RTE); Semantic interoperability layer (SIL); Data and knowledge management software [incl. API] (DKMS); Machine learning predictors [incl. surrogate models] (MLP); Physics-based modelling (PBM); Experimental characterization facilities [incl. ELN] (EXP); Pilots [incl. sensorics / on-line characterization] (PIL); LDS: Large-data storage (LDS); DT visualization and human-computer interaction (DTV). For convenience, they are listed again with their abbreviations in Table 5, [Appendix D](#). There, also an additional category for Non-functional requirements is included.

High level analysis of the requirements based on interviews

T4.1 focuses on gathering and analysing the knowledge infrastructure requirements for BatCAT project's use cases. This includes the integration of the CaosDB data model and ensuring interoperability with BIG-MAP. The analysis consists of various levels of requirements, from low-level technical specifics to high-level functional needs, working in parallel with the landscape analysis in T4.3. An agile approach has been adopted to facilitate dynamic consultation with a broad spectrum of stakeholders within and outside the BatCAT consortium.

After interviewing domain-knowledge experts (representatives of partners within BatCAT) and analysing questionnaires, a list of key requirements was formed. The list can be split into functional and non-functional

requirements. By defining them at the early stage of the project each of the project partners can better plan their contribution to the project as well as mitigate risks related to the knowledge base infrastructure.

An anonymised list of key requirements extracted from the interviews, questionnaires, and cross-WP exchanges is given in the form of user stories in [Appendix C](#). Below we highlight some of those requirements in a narrative form.

Functional Requirements

In the second stage of the interviews, several key technical requirements were outlined that are crucial for battery manufacturing and testing systems. The first major requirement is the separation of data into three distinct data vaults. This involves creating an internal vault that stores company-wide data unrelated to specific projects, a second vault that houses project-related data accessible only within the company, and a third common database intended for **data that can be shared with external collaborators or across the project partners**. This separation ensures that data is securely managed according to its sensitivity and intended use, thereby maintaining the integrity and privacy of both internal and project-specific information.

A significant focus is also placed on managing time series data, particularly for individual batteries and cell testing. This requirement highlights the need for **robust data storage** and retrieval systems that can effectively handle the continuous stream of data generated during battery tests. In case of REDOX flow batteries, the flow rate is identified as a unique and critical parameter that must be accurately captured and analysed. This distinct parameter is crucial for understanding and optimizing the performance of this type of batteries, which operate differently compared to traditional battery types.

Another important aspect is **the consideration of material properties and manufacturing-related data**. Certain project partners recognize that these factors can significantly impact battery performance and parameters. Therefore, the system must be capable of capturing and correlating this data with battery test results to enable comprehensive analysis and improvements in battery design and manufacturing processes.

The need for **version control and the ability to store iterations** in the database is also emphasized. This capability is essential for tracking the evolution of testing procedures, data, and battery designs over time. It ensures that all changes are documented, and historical data is preserved, enabling better analysis and decision-making.

The requirement for **high-frequency data collection** is particularly demanding, with a need to capture a high number of measurements per second at 16-bit resolution, although temperature measurements may require less precision. This level of data granularity is necessary to accurately monitor the performance of batteries under various conditions and to detect any issues or anomalies in real time.

One of the project partners has in-house production of Battery Management Systems (BMS), which eliminates the need for third-party electronics. This internal capability allows for greater control over the integration and functionality of the BMS with their testing and data management systems, ensuring that the system meets their specific requirements without reliance on external suppliers.

In summary, these key requirements are aimed to improve the design of the future system, helping to develop a highly specialized and secure system for managing battery testing data, with an emphasis on precision, control, and adaptability to accommodate the unique characteristics of different battery types.

Non-Functional Requirements

Non-functional requirements (NFRs) define the quality attributes, system constraints, or overall characteristics of a system that specify how it should perform, rather than what it should do. Unlike functional requirements, which describe specific behaviours or functions of the system (e.g., "the system must allow users to log in"),

non-functional requirements focus on aspects such as performance, security, usability, and scalability. In [Appendix D](#), they are tagged as “NFCT”.

Requirements on mappings from high-level to low-level

Dedicated internal discussions addressed the mapping needs between low-level (schemas used by CaosDB as well as raw data, e.g. tabular data in csv files), mid-level (the ontologies) and high-level (ASP logic, used within the DSS system). In order for the DSS to query the knowledge base, facts from the knowledge base are to be translated into the representation used by the ASP framework. The main outcome of those was that that the existent CaosDB interfaces already address requirements for the mapping to clingo⁶ (a system for ASP). In fact, it is not necessary to use OWL as an intermediate representation of the facts, they could be translated from CaosDB to clingo directly (there are python libraries for both systems). Especially, when working on raw data (say from a SQL data base) the mapping could also affect performance or become an unnecessary burden. However, as modularity, loose coupling and usage of standard technologies are typical non-functional requirements of complex systems a mapping from CaosDB to OWL and from OWL to the ASP framework is a “Should” requirement.

Optimization questionnaire: analysis of the answers

In this section, the responses to the questionnaire from [Appendix A](#), including the overall votes from both internal and external groups, are presented for the following categories: logic-based, MCO-based, on-chip, and machine learning prediction problems.

Figure 4.2 The logic-based scheduling problems ordered by the number of votes

⁶ See <https://potassco.org/>

Figure 4.2 shows that regarding the logic-based scheduling problems, “Design of Simulation (DoS)” and “Design of Experiment (DoE)” are the top concerns, each with 9 responses (47.4%). “Energy Consumption Monitoring” follows with 8 responses (42.1%), while “Production Workflow Optimization” and “Quality Control Decision Making” both have 7 responses (36.8%). The least mentioned problems, each with 1 response (5.3%), include “Inventory Management Optimization”, “Equipment Performance Analysis”, and “Human Resource Allocation”. This highlights key areas needing optimization focus, especially in simulation, experimental design, and energy monitoring.

Figure 4.3 The MCO problems ordered by the number of votes

Figure 4.3 displays the most frequently selected MCO-Optimization Problems, with “Slurry Formulation Optimization” and “Design of Simulation (DoS)” both leading at 9 responses each (45%). Following closely are “Electrode Material Selection”, “Coating Thickness and Uniformity”, “Electrolyte Composition”, and “Design of Experiment (DoE)” each at 8 responses (40%). The least mentioned problem is “Waste Reduction in Manufacturing” with 4 responses (20%). This visualization highlights the areas with the highest perceived optimization needs.

Figure 4.4 The on-Cell logic-based/MCO problems ordered by the number of votes

Figure 4.4 highlights that, regarding on-chip hybrid optimization problems, “Design of Simulation (DoS)” as the most frequently mentioned issue, with 10 responses (52.6%). “Design of Experiment (DoE)” follows closely with 9 responses (47.4%). Both “Cell Capacity Optimization” and “Aging Rate Reduction” received 7 responses each (36.8%). The least cited problems, with only 1 response each (5.3%), include “Voltage Consistency Calibration” and “Safety Mechanism Compliance”. This chart indicates a strong focus on simulation and experimental design as critical optimization areas.

Figure 4.5 The possible machine learning-based prediction problems ordered by the number of votes

Figure 4.5 illustrates the top Machine Learning-Based Prediction Problems. “Material Performance Prediction” is the most critical, with 66.7% of the votes. “Mapping between Simulation Methods” and “Interpolation between Simulation/Experimental Data” are also highly valued, with 55.6% and 50%, respectively. The chart highlights the importance of predicting performance and ensuring data consistency as well as interpolation accuracy, critical for effective machine learning applications in battery design.

5. Conclusions

This document has summarized the methods and results of BatCAT T4.1 and T4.3, and its content will serve as a basis for following project tasks, notably T4.2 - *Knowledge base for cell manufacturing*, T4.4 - *Metadata standardization* and optimization tasks from WP5 – *Digital Twin technology*.

We used a combination of interviews, collaborative workshops and questionnaires, mostly with project partners but also with a few representative external experts. As a result, we collected/formulated 56 user stories grouped under 23 epics and about 50 between competency questions and facts, representing the knowledge needed within BatCAT to address the project use cases and requirements for the knowledge-based data infrastructure. All stories and questions are assigned unique identifiers and are tagged along relevant dimensions to facilitate their uptake in the following project tasks (see in particular the mapping of architecture components to WPs).

An extensive questionnaire on optimization, answered by 19 participants, provided a ranking of concrete optimization problems for various types, namely logic-based, MCO-based, on-chip, and machine learning prediction problems. This constitutes concrete input for other WPs, especially WP5, by pointing out what concrete scenarios are to be prioritized.

This concludes the work of T4.1 and T4.3, and we believe it covers the bulk of information needed. However, the list of requirements will necessarily be a living entity as the project is in its initial phase, and extensions or adjustments could be made based on the project needs as it develops further.

6. Acknowledgements

We warmly thank all project partners who participated in the interviews and the interactive workshop of month 6. We also thank the external experts who kindly agreed to be interviewed and answered the questionnaire for their valuable input. We acknowledge use of the BIG-MAP Archive, which among other functionalities enables data sharing within the Battery2030+ network.

Appendix A: Questionnaire on optimization

Requirements Analysis - Possible BatCAT Optimization/Prediction Problems

Please select below battery-related optimization and prediction problems you already address OR will/could realistically address within the next 3 years.

The problems are grouped into four classes. **The categorization of the problems was based on the following assumptions:** MCO-based techniques are ideal for optimizing multiple conflicting objectives, handling both continuous and discrete variables. ASP-based methods excel in complex logical reasoning and decision-making with discrete solutions. Integrated MCO-ASP approaches are best for problems requiring both numerical optimization and rule-based decision-making, accommodating a mix of continuous and discrete variables.

Note: When selecting an optimization problem for our BatCAT decision support system, it is essential to verify that the data sourced from BatCAT partners—whether obtained from your databases or simulations—matches the requirements of the selected problems. Without appropriate data, the optimization process cannot be effectively applied.

Figure 6.1 Snapshot of the webform for the optimization questionnaire (page 1).

First Name, Last Name *

Your answer

Institution *

Your answer

Your position with respect to BatCAT *

Internal (I work on the project)

External (I do not work on the project)

In which of these roles do you best identify yourself? *

Manufacturing use-case owner

Experimentalist

Digital twin technology user

Simulation researcher

Developer of a related platform

Policy expert

Customer

(IT Systems) Administrator

Figure 6.2. Snapshot of the webform for the optimization questionnaire (page 2)

Possible MCO-Optimization Problems

- Electrode Material Selection: Maximize energy density and minimize cost, constrained by material availability and safety standards.
- Slurry Formulation Optimization: Optimize viscosity for coating quality and maximize homogeneity, with constraints being ingredient ratios and environmental impact.
- Coating Thickness and Uniformity: Minimize thickness variation and optimize thickness for energy capacity, constrained by machine precision and drying times.
- Drying Process Efficiency: Minimize energy consumption and optimize drying time for quality, with temperature ranges and material properties as constraints.
- Calendering Pressure and Gap: Optimize for electrode density and maintain material integrity, constrained by material strength and machine capabilities.
- Electrolyte Composition: Maximize ionic conductivity and minimize cost, with chemical stability and compatibility with electrode materials as constraints.
- Cell Assembly Precision: Maximize alignment accuracy and minimize assembly defects, constrained by tolerance levels and automation capabilities.
- Formation Cycle Optimization: Optimize cycle time for efficiency and maximize cell longevity, with charge/discharge rates and thermal management as constraints.
- Production Line Energy Efficiency: Minimize total energy consumption and maximize throughput, constrained by machine efficiency and production volume.
- Waste Reduction in Manufacturing: Minimize material waste and optimize recycling processes, with recycling technology and regulatory requirements as constraints.
- Design of Experiment (DoE): Quantitative optimization of experimental parameters / boundary conditions to obtain the most valuable expected information outcome
- Design of Simulation (DoS): Quantitative optimization of experimental parameters / boundary conditions to obtain the most valuable expected information outcome

Figure 6.3. Snapshot of the webform for the optimization questionnaire (page 3)

Possible On-Cell Logic-Based Reasoning/MCO-based Optimization Problems

- Electrode Layering Precision: Achieve precise layering of electrode materials to ensure uniform cell performance, with material properties and layering technology as constraints.
- Cell Capacity Optimization: Maximize the energy capacity of battery cells while ensuring longevity, with physical dimensions and chemical limitations as constraints.
- Thermal Management Efficiency: Optimize thermal management systems to enhance battery safety and performance, with material thermal properties and cooling technologies as constraints.
- Electrolyte Stability Assurance: Ensure electrolyte chemical stability for extended battery life, with chemical compatibility and operational temperature ranges as constraints.
- Cell Balancing Accuracy: Achieve accurate cell balancing in battery packs to maximize overall efficiency, with cell variance and balancing algorithms as constraints.
- Voltage Consistency Calibration: Calibrate cells to maintain voltage consistency across a battery pack, with cell manufacturing tolerances and calibration methods as constraints.
- Impedance Minimization Strategy: Minimize electrical impedance to improve battery efficiency, with electrode material and cell design as constraints.
- Safety Mechanism Compliance: Integrate and verify safety mechanisms to prevent overcharging and thermal runaway, with industry safety standards and cell chemistry as constraints.
- Aging Rate Reduction: Slow down the aging rate of battery cells to extend their usable life, with material degradation processes and cell usage patterns as constraints.
- Charging Protocol Optimization: Develop optimized charging protocols to enhance battery life and performance, with cell chemistry and charging technology as constraints.
- Energy Density Enhancement: Increase the energy density of battery cells while maintaining safety, with material innovations and cell architecture as constraints.
- Design of Experiment (DoE): Integration of quantitative (MCO) and qualitative (ASP) based parameter selection.
- Design of Simulation (DoS): Integration of quantitative (MCO) and qualitative (ASP) based parameter selection.

If you have any optimization suggestions that are not mentioned above, please share them here:

Your answer

Figure 6.4. Snapshot of the webform for the optimization questionnaire (page 4)

Machine learning-based prediction problems:

- Lifetime Prediction
- Capacity Fade Modeling
- Thermal Behavior Forecasting
- Charge Rate Optimization
- Degradation Factor Identification
- Energy Density Estimation
- Safety Incident Prediction
- Manufacturing Defect Detection
- Material Performance Prediction
- Recycling Efficiency Projection
- Temperature Impact Analysis
- Pressure Variation Effects
- Interpolation between simulation/experimental data
- Mapping between simulation methods, e.g., molecular to continuum level
- Surrogates representing model class behaviour in MCO-based bespoke model parameterization
- Modelling the expected information outcome from experiments or simulations for use in MCO-based DoE/DoS
- Imputation of missing/inaccurate data in time series from sensors
- Consistency checks / raising flags on implausible data

If you have other suggestions for machine learning-based prediction tasks, please share them here:

Your answer

Figure 6.5. Snapshot of the webform for the optimization questionnaire (page 5)

Appendix B: Short set of questions to support the data and metadata landscape

Selected questions to support BatCAT Data and Metadata landscape

Version: 1.2

Instructions: If you have little time, please focus on the **text in blue**.

Context

Our aim in brief: To understand who within BatCAT will generate / use data, and what types? Who will search / browse data, and with what query? Is there a (internal or widely spread) vocabulary / schema / reference / book / standard already used in BatCAT institutions and perspective users to describe batteries and their manufacturing?

Accordingly, we will collect: information about "Data types" BatCAT needs to handle; relevant information on characterization instruments, sensors/devices, software; (public or internal) documents, manuals that define the terminology currently used within BatCAT institutions and perspective users; example queries; requirements from data consumer side.

Questions for you

Your data in a nutshell:

- **Please describe in one/two lines the main type of data and metadata you/your institution handle in relation to BatCAT** [Examples 1: modelling data, related to in-house software; data formats are proprietary, metadata is from the software or user-defined. Example 2: Experimental data, mostly in Excel or CSV format, with headers defined by a group of experimentalists, in house. Example 3: sensor data from manufacturing line, metadata from the device vendor, complies with standard ISO-XXX]

General information (cataloguing and status)

- **Data type (high level)** [Characterization, simulation, manufacturing, sensor/monitoring, battery design, ...]
- Data type (mid-high level)
- **Is the data in a database NOW?** [Yes/No, Type of database] (relational DB, non-relational, graph DB, etc.)
- How long is the data stored/needed for? [If this or the need WILL change once BatCAT data space is up, specify it]

Data generation

- **Who generates the data?** [Device, Software, Human, etc]

- Is this data (typically) Input or Output (or both) of some device / software? [I, O, I/O]
 - Of which device/software? [Device/software name]
- Is it stream data? [Yes/No]
 - Is it generated regularly or in an event-based manner?

Data structure

- Structure (file formats, etc) [Use a brief text to describe the data structure]
 - **Is the data structure documented? (Yes/No)**
 - Link to data structure documentation
- Are data formats:
 - binary, human readable? (B, H)
 - Open-source? [Yes/No]
 - Documented? [Yes/No]

Metadata

- **Data type in more detail: keywords (i.e., provide some key terms)**
- **How is the metadata given?** (e.g., column headers)
- **Does it follow a schema?** [Yes/No]
 - Name/link of schema followed
- Are ontologies already used at your institute in relation to these data? (Yes/No)
 - Name+acronyms of the ontology(ies), URL
- Standards (ISO-like, or "de facto") used in the use case or BatCAT in relation to these data

Terminology sources

- **What are the sources of terminology you / your institution uses for metadata?** (E.g., public or internal documents, manuals, books, ISO standards, etc., to describe battery manufacturing)
- How broadly are these used? (By individual user, group, project, institution, community, nation, EU, worldwide, ...)

Data access

- Data provider/publisher [name or type, e.g., experimental scientist]
- Data owner [name or type, e.g., experimental scientist]
- Data access rights [license, free/at a cost, etc.]

Data quality

- Is data quality addressed? Which aspect? (e.g., completeness, reliability)
- Are there typical / known quality issues (e.g., inconsistencies) with these data?

Searching / querying the data

- What questions are you (or others) likely to ask to search through and (re-)use your stored data? (E.g., identify all samples belonging to a given batch, find simulation results using a certain force field and describing material X, etc.)

Process and product design / optimization

- What are the (main) parameters you vary and the (main) quantities you would like to optimize in the manufacturing / simulation / experimental process? And for the final product? [Please point out if it is an actual scenario (=something you do already), or an imagined realistic scenario. E.g., vary the solvent composition to minimize its viscosity, change numerical simulation parameters or compare different methods/engines for best trade-off between precision and computational cost, ...]

Appendix C: Epics and user stories, including prioritization

In this section, we give user stories and epics in Table 2. Epics are highlighted in blue and the ordering is such that the USs falling under an epic follow it. In Table 1 we give the property and values used for the tags and prioritization. Note that epics are used to group user stories; as such, they are not assigned a design target or a priority value. Similarly, they do not fall under broader stories.

Property	Values
Story type	US: User story; EP: Epic
Design target	(0) NFCT: Non-functional requirement; (1) DSS: Decision support system [incl. DoE+DoS]; (2) KBC: Knowledge base - central; (3) KBP: Knowledge base - peripheral; (4) RTE: Real-time environment [incl. actionable models]; (5) SIL: Semantic interoperability layer; (6) DKMS: Data and knowledge management software [incl. API]; (7) MLP: Machine learning predictors [incl. surrogate models]; (8) PBM: Physics-based modelling; (9) EXP: Experimental characterization facilities [incl. ELN]; (10) PIL: Pilots [incl. sensorics / on-line characterization]; (11) LDS: Large-data storage; (12) DTV: DT visualization and human-computer interaction
Role	(1) MI: Manufacturing use-case owner, internal; (2) EI: Experimentalist, internal; (3) EE: Experimentalist, external; (4) SI: Simulation researcher, internal; (5) DI: Digital twin technology user, internal; (6) DE: Developer of a related platform, external; (7) PE: Policy expert, external; (8) CE: Customer, external; (9) AI: IT Administrator, internal
Priority	M=Must; S=Should; C=Could; W=Won't

Table 1. Properties and values of tags used for user stories

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_AI_1	(n/a - epic)	AI	Define the workflow and timelines for typical updates clearly and communicate them to the developers so that this information reaches them	Facilitate efficient software development by clear responsibility and separation of tasks, so that developers can focus on their work and I on mine	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_NFCT_AI_1	NFCT	AI	Follow good practices and solidly established governance rules for all BatCAT processes and components that are respected by all team members	EP_AI_1 (Define the workflow and timelines for typical updates clearly and communicate them to the developers so that this information reaches them)	EP_AI_1	W ⁷
EP_AI_2	(n/a - epic)	AI	Rely on established technology and workflows for IT system administration	Manage many different systems at the same time	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_KBP_AI_1	KBP	AI	Install, update and maintain the system using one of the common container technologies (e.g. docker)	EP_AI_2 (Rely on established technology and workflows for IT system administration)	EP_AI_2	S
US_SIL_AI_1	SIL	AI	Define a (meta)data schema which is then adopted/respected by the other users such that I can guarantee FAIR data management practices	EP_AI_2 (Rely on established technology and workflows for IT system administration)	EP_AI_2	W ⁸
EP_AI_3	(n/a - epic)	AI	Comply with our internal rules related to data security and data protection	It is simply my job to do this.	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_KBP_AI_2	KBP	AI	Control who has access to which information (internal users, i.e. from my institution and possibly external users, i.e. cross-institutional)	EP_AI_3 (Comply with our internal rules related to data security and data protection)	EP_AI_3	M

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics

⁷ This is not doable for *all* BatCAT processes and components. A softer version, for *main/selected* processes and components could be considered.

⁸ It should not be the IT administrator, but the BatCAT consortium that defines such metadata schema.

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_DI_1	(n/a - epic)	DI	Track parameters and materials used for manufacturing of flow-batteries that have a unique set of parameters	Establish a version control system for iterations of flow batteries	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_SIL_DI_1	SIL	DI	Obtain/read set of material IDs prior to manufacturing (QR, Barcode, etc.)	EP_DI_1 (Track parameters and materials used for manufacturing of flow-batteries that have a unique set of parameters)	EP_DI_1	S
US_EXP_DI_1	EXP	DI	Perform required test on assembled batteries, store data, link it to materials used	EP_DI_1 (Track parameters and materials used for manufacturing of flow-batteries that have a unique set of parameters)	EP_DI_1	M
US_KBP_DI_1	KBP	DI	Save the data obtained during testing and create a new state in the version control	EP_DI_1 (Track parameters and materials used for manufacturing of flow-batteries that have a unique set of parameters)	EP_DI_1	M
US_KBC_DI_1	KBC	DI	Compare performance of batteries batch against the simulation model or the ones already existing in the DB	EP_DI_1 (Track parameters and materials used for manufacturing of flow-batteries that have a unique set of parameters)	EP_DI_1	M
EP_DI_2	(n/a - epic)	DI	Use a transparent digital twin, meeting a series of requirements for reliability and interpretability	Comply with all institutional, legal, and customers' requirements for transparency	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_DTV_DI_1	DTV	DI	Clearly distinguish and eventually compare the actual/measured and the predicted values for the various battery properties and other manufacturing parameters	EP_DI_2 (Use a transparent digital twin, meeting a series of requirements for reliability and interpretability)	EP_DI_2	S
US_DTV_DI_2	DTV	DI	Be able to clearly see what control parameters can/cannot be tuned in a certain manufacturing process	EP_DI_2 (Use a transparent digital twin, meeting a series of requirements for reliability and interpretability)	EP_DI_2	C

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
US_KBC_DI_2	KBC	DI	For statements (and metadata values) in the KB, knowing whether they were manually or automatically generated (in case there is a non-negligible fraction of statements of the second type). For example: was the data "topic" assigned manually or by an NLP tool?	EP_DI_2 (Use a transparent digital twin, meeting a series of requirements for reliability and interpretability)	EP_DI_2	M
US_DTV_DI_3	DTV	DI	Be able to select options in an easy and coarse way, for example as a traffic light system (good, middle, bad), for properties where this is meaningful. [I would still like to know how that is assigned, e.g., how was a parameter space binned into three regions]	EP_DI_2 (Use a transparent digital twin, meeting a series of requirements for reliability and interpretability)	EP_DI_2	S
US_KBC_DI_2	KBC	DI	Clearly know whether data are "raw" (i.e., as produced by a software/device) or were "processed" in some way. Which devices/tools (name+version+URL to info) generated and eventually processed it.	EP_DI_2 (Use a transparent digital twin, meeting a series of requirements for reliability and interpretability)	EP_DI_2	M

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_DI_3	(n/a - epic)	DI	Make informed decisions on the selection and use of ML models	Comply with all institutional, legal, and customers' requirements for transparency	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_MLP_DI_1	MLP	DI	Select ML predictors / simulations that work in real-time or faster or slower, and select whether they are for short term or long term (usually, in ML, long term means more than 7 points in the future)	EP_DI_3 (Make informed decisions on the selection and use of ML models)	EP_DI_3	S
US_MLP_DI_2	MLP	DI	Access/know the level of accuracy of a ML predictor (e.g., as defined by the mean square relative error between ground truth and prediction) - (e.g., 0.0X, 0.00X - per cent or per mille)	EP_DI_3 (Make informed decisions on the selection and use of ML models)	EP_DI_3	M
EP_EI_1	(n/a - epic)	EI	Track the whole history (across laboratories) of each experimental sample being characterized in BatCAT	Gathering complete experimental data on batteries	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_KBC_EI_1	KBC	EI	Assign a unique identifier to each sample within my lab and across BatCAT	EP_EI_1 (Track the whole history (across laboratories) of each experimental sample being characterized in BatCAT)	EP_EI_1	M
US_EXP_EI_1	EXP	EI	Record all the sample input and preparation conditions (synthesis procedure, vendor of materials)	EP_EI_1 (Track the whole history (across laboratories) of each experimental sample being characterized in BatCAT)	EP_EI_1	M
US_KBP_EI_1	KBP	EI	Record all processes undergone by a sample, including artificial / accelerated ageing	EP_EI_1 (Track the whole history (across laboratories) of each experimental sample being characterized in BatCAT)	EP_EI_1	M
US_EXP_EI_2	EXP	EI	Record information on the experimental device used (vendor, machine/equipment ID/number, channel ID/number) for characterization, as part of metadata for characterization data	EP_EI_1 (Track the whole history (across laboratories) of each experimental sample being characterized in BatCAT)	EP_EI_1	C

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_EI_2	(n/a - epic)	EI	Efficient integration of (experimental) data from multiple sources into a single knowledge base	Efficient data interoperability across institutions and over time	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_EXP_EI_3	EXP	EI	Upload data from my experimental device (e.g., potentiostat/galvanostat) to ELN/OpenSemanticLab directly (with little, and ideally no manual input needed)	EP_EI_2 (Efficient integration of (experimental) data from multiple sources into a single knowledge base)	EP_EI_2	C
US_KBP_EI_2	KBP	EI	Track new (i.e., previously not recorded) metadata for my experimental data	EP_EI_2 (Efficient integration of (experimental) data from multiple sources into a single knowledge base)	EP_EI_2	C
US_EXP_EI_4	EXP	EI	Use the metadata schema which has been agreed upon within the consortium to annotate my data	EP_EI_2 (Efficient integration of (experimental) data from multiple sources into a single knowledge base)	EP_EI_2	S
US_KBC_EI_2	KBC	EI	Export a collection of data sets with metadata attached in order to publish my results	EP_EI_2 (Efficient integration of (experimental) data from multiple sources into a single knowledge base)	EP_EI_2	C
EP_EI_3	(n/a - epic)	EI	Classify and categorize scrap materials from manufacturing, returning results to pilot operator and/or supplier	Use experimental facilities to reduce the scrap rate in battery manufacturing	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_EXP_EI_5	EXP	EI	Record parameters and metadata of a material received from a supplier	EP_EI_3 (Classify and categorize scrap materials from manufacturing, returning results to pilot operator and/or supplier)	EP_EI_3	
US_PIL_EI_1	PIL	EI	Record parameters obtained during testing of battery performance and link them against the materials used	EP_EI_3 (Classify and categorize scrap materials from manufacturing, returning results to pilot operator and/or supplier)	EP_EI_3	
US_EXP_EI_6	EXP	EI	Rate materials performance	EP_EI_3 (Classify and categorize scrap materials from manufacturing, returning results to pilot operator and/or supplier)	EP_EI_3	

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_EI_4	(n/a - epic)	EI	Work with the BatCAT data space and the ELN as part of my established work routines the way they are now, with minimal required modifications	Have consistent research workflows and keep doing experiments and reporting according to our established practices	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_EXP_EI_7	EXP	EI	Login with the user account of my home institution, because I don't want to sign-up for just another system	EP_EI_4 (Work with the BatCAT data space and the ELN as part of my established work routines the way they are now, with minimal required modifications)	EP_EI_4	C ⁹
US_KBC_EI_3	KBC	EI	Search the BatCAT data space from a central entry point in order to have access to data that is spread over peripheral systems without the need to actually access all of those systems separately	EP_EI_4 (Work with the BatCAT data space and the ELN as part of my established work routines the way they are now, with minimal required modifications)	EP_EI_4	M
US_DKMS_EI_1	DKMS	EI	Access the knowledge base via my personal computer, laptop, or mobile phone regardless of my operating system because otherwise I don't want to install more software on my devices and I want to connect using different devices from time to time (lab, office, home, traveling)	EP_EI_4 (Work with the BatCAT data space and the ELN as part of my established work routines the way they are now, with minimal required modifications)	EP_EI_4	S
EP_EI_5	(n/a - epic)	EI	Ensure that the experiments done in BatCAT are the experiments that are needed	Make effective use of our working hours and technical/laboratory equipment (and materials)	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_DSS_EI_1	DSS	EI	Access DoE functionality and obtain a set of recommendations for experiments required by a materials set to best complement all that already is known	EP_EI_5 (Ensure that the experiments done in BatCAT are the experiments that are needed)	EP_EI_5	M

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

⁹ We note that ORCID could alternatively be used, as all researchers involved will have one.

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_MI_1	(n/a - epic)	MI	Only use a digital tool in a production environment if it is trustworthy and reliable, including a clear assessment of numerical uncertainty throughout	Comply with all institutional, legal, and customers' requirements for operational reliability	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_KBC_MI_1	KBC	MI	Obtain uncertainty metric(s) associated with every quantitative value that I obtain from anything developed in BatCAT	EP_MI_1 (Only use a digital tool in a production environment if it is trustworthy and reliable, including a clear assessment of numerical uncertainty throughout)	EP_MI_1	M
US_RTE_MI_1	RTE	MI	Confidence intervals and clear/reliable assertions on the operational limitations (valid operating conditions) must be present for any recommendation or intervention by the actionable modelling	EP_MI_1 (Only use a digital tool in a production environment if it is trustworthy and reliable, including a clear assessment of numerical uncertainty throughout)	EP_MI_1	M
EP_MI_2	(n/a - epic)	MI	Make good use of resources within the BatCAT project, without jeopardizing process safety	Make effective use of our working hours and technical/laboratory equipment (and materials)	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_PIL_MI_1	PIL	MI	Choose sensors' connection type as appropriate for their needed reaction time scales (e.g., fastest ones for safety-critical measurements)	EP_MI_2 (Make good use of resources within the BatCAT project, without jeopardizing process safety)	EP_MI_2	M

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_SI_1	(n/a - epic)	SI	Work with a knowledge base and interoperability environment that makes my simulation workflows efficient and my simulation results easily reusable for surrogate modelling	Contribute meaningfully to a multiphysics simulation project, where lower-level methods pass on quantities to higher-level methods, and eventually to surrogate and actionable modelling	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_DSS_SI_1	DSS	SI	Use the MCO-based model parameterization methodology, known from the literature and previous work, for a problem such as parameterizing an ion model in combination with a water model	EP_SI_1 (Work with a knowledge base and interoperability environment that makes my simulation workflows efficient and my simulation results easily reusable for surrogate modelling)	EP_SI_1	S
US_PBM_SI_1	PBM	SI	Receive the simulation data that are necessary for a surrogate model that feeds into my simulations, e.g., a surrogate model for transport properties in case of the continuum simulator of VRFB's using FEniCS	EP_SI_1 (Work with a knowledge base and interoperability environment that makes my simulation workflows efficient and my simulation results easily reusable for surrogate modelling)	EP_SI_1	S
US_MLP_SI_1	MLP	SI	Be able to construct the surrogate models that I will be using myself (not having to request them from a project partner, but doing it directly), including validation and testing and a clear indication of uncertainty/confidence	EP_SI_1 (Work with a knowledge base and interoperability environment that makes my simulation workflows efficient and my simulation results easily reusable for surrogate modelling)	EP_SI_1	C
US_PBM_SI_2	PBM	SI	Construct a potential modelling workflow that can predict simulation cell/battery system properties/behaviour from known parameters, based on choices available in the knowledge base.	EP_SI_1 (Work with a knowledge base and interoperability environment that makes my simulation workflows efficient and my simulation results easily reusable for surrogate modelling)	EP_SI_1	S
US_DSS_SI_2	DSS	SI	Determine decision criteria for choosing between potential modelling workflows. These should be stored in the knowledge base.	EP_SI_1 (Work with a knowledge base and interoperability environment that makes my simulation workflows efficient and my simulation results easily reusable for surrogate modelling)	EP_SI_1	C

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
US_PBM_SI_3	PBM	SI	Implement simulation workflows using specific software, licensing and hardware setups (based on available choices in KB).	EP_SI_1 (Work with a knowledge base and interoperability environment that makes my simulation workflows efficient and my simulation results easily reusable for surrogate modelling)	EP_SI_1	M
US_SIL_SI_1	SIL	SI	Mapping of outputs to inputs between models in a workflow (e.g., I want to map the output of Lattice Boltzmann to input of CFD). Mappings should be stored, retrievable and modifiable.	EP_SI_1 (Work with a knowledge base and interoperability environment that makes my simulation workflows efficient and my simulation results easily reusable for surrogate modelling)	EP_SI_1	M
EP_SI_2	(n/a - epic)		Implement quality control in simulation and establish accuracy and validity of simulation workflows/results	Contribute meaningfully to a multiphysics simulation project, where lower-level methods pass on quantities to higher-level methods, and eventually to surrogate and actionable modelling	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_KBC_SI_1	KBC	SI	Validate simulation results based on experimental data in the knowledge base; this may require relating simulation data to experimental data in some way (correlations, etc.)	EP_SI_2 (implement quality control in simulation and establish accuracy and validity of simulation workflows/results)	EP_SI_2	M
EP_SI_3	(n/a - epic)	SI	Exchange data relevant to simulation with the BatCAT data space in a way that does not disrupt simulation and data processing workflows	Integrate simulation workflows and/or their results and/or input to them with the BatCAT data space	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_DKMS_SI_1	DKMS	SI	Interact with the knowledge base by means of a library in my preferred programming language (e.g. Python, Julia, R?) because I want to fetch and push data automatically and directly from my scripts	EP_SI_3 (Exchange data relevant to simulation with the BatCAT data space in a way that does not disrupt simulation and data processing workflows)	EP_SI_3	W ¹⁰

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

¹⁰ It is not feasible to work with *all* people's private favourite programming languages.

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
US_LDS_SI_1	LDS	SI	Access (read) and retrieve (get) data from the large data storage at a speed fast enough to not constitute a bottleneck to my work	EP_SI_3 (Exchange data relevant to simulation with the BatCAT data space in a way that does not disrupt simulation and data processing workflows)	EP_SI_3	M
EP_CE_1	(n/a - epic)	CE	Adhere to my company's high standards on IP protection that typically apply in an industrial setting, e.g., for commercially sensitive data	It is simply my job to do this	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_DKMS_CE_1	DKMS	CE	Being able to use BatCAT tools on my own data, while keeping my data within my company	EP_CE_1 (Adhere to my company's high standards on IP protection that typically apply in an industrial setting, e.g., for commercially sensitive data)	EP_CE_1	S
EP_CE_2	(n/a - epic)	CE	Employ the BatCAT DT as a robust digital tool that is resilient to changes within its various components and its users' environments	Have a resilient digital infrastructure that will not break down once normal changes and updates are done	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_NFCT_CE_1	NFCT	CE	Be informed about the governance processes and good practices, specially about maintenance, in place for BatCAT components, and be able to confirm that the processes and practices are resilient	EP_CE_2 (Employ the BatCAT DT as a robust digital tool that is resilient to changes within its various components and its users' environments)	EP_CE_2	C ¹¹

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

¹¹ We are going to TRL 5, so it is not crucial to be able to inform external customers about maintenance.

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_DE_1	(n/a - epic)	DE	Enable interoperability and exchange of knowledge, including models and data, on LIB cell manufacturing between KiproBatt and BatCAT	Achieve synergy between KiproBatt and other digital twin and battery manufacturing digitalization platforms	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_SIL_DE_1	SIL	DE	Use mutually agreed interfaces specified as OO-LD schema for data exchange	EP_DE_1 (Enable interoperability and exchange of knowledge, including models and data, on LIB cell manufacturing between KiproBatt and BatCAT)	EP_DE_1	M
US_SIL_DE_2	SIL	DE	Rely on agreed domain ontologies that go beyond what has been standardized so far; this must account for the concepts listed in the KiproBatt wiki (e.g., separator foil, https://kiprobatt.de/wiki/Category:OSLa24dc426cfb44c8a93c18e176147c593)	EP_DE_1 (Enable interoperability and exchange of knowledge, including models and data, on LIB cell manufacturing between KiproBatt and BatCAT)	EP_DE_1	M
US_KBC_DE_1	KBC	DE	Mutually recognize PIDs for all elements on which information is exchanged, including surrogate models, samples, sensors, and characterization and manufacturing equipment	EP_DE_1 (Enable interoperability and exchange of knowledge, including models and data, on LIB cell manufacturing between KiproBatt and BatCAT)	EP_DE_1	C
EP_DE_2	(n/a - epic)	DE	Develop metadata standards such that they can be used across organizations and projects without unnecessary redundant work such as adjusting the expressivity multiple times	Efficient data interoperability across institutions and over time	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_SIL_DE_3	SIL	DE	Follow a design specification for the ontologies for epistemic metadata that is in line with the requirements of ASP reasoning and the KGA XAIR WG's requirements	EP_DE_2 (Develop metadata standards such that they can be used across organizations and projects without unnecessary redundant work such as adjusting the expressivity multiple times)	EP_DE_2	C

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_EE_1	(n/a - epic)	EE	Ensure best practices for experimental data quality and fidelity	Best practices for scientific data quality	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_SIL_EE_1	SIL	EE	Be able to access uncertainty and confidence levels as part of experimental data in BatCAT. Suitable data-quality checks and guarantees are in place and documented in the metadata	EP_EE_1 (Ensure best practices for experimental data quality and fidelity)	EP_EE_1	M
EP_PE_1	(n/a - epic)	PE ¹²	Enable manufacturers of redox flow batteries to reliably calculate the entries required for the digital product passport of redox flow batteries	Help the flow batteries industry sector comply with European regulations to retain access to market and so that policies are successfully implemented.	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_DSS_PE_1	DSS	PE	At process and product design stage, enable VRFB manufacturers to predict the carbon footprint (and other metrics relevant to the DPP) of VRFBs	EP_PE_1 (Enable RFB manufacturers to reliably calculate the entries required for the digital product passport of redox flow batteries)	EP_PE_1	S
US_RTE_PE_1	RTE	PE	Enable VRFB manufacturers to quantify and track resource consumption (in particular, the carbon footprint) during the manufacturing process at real time.	EP_PE_1 (Enable RFB manufacturers to reliably calculate the entries required for the digital product passport of redox flow batteries)	EP_PE_1	S
US_KBP_PE_1	KBP	PE	Enforce minimum standards securing that any recommended digital twin / data space software implements robust measures to protect industrial users against breaches, unauthorized sharing, or exploitation of sensitive information	EP_PE_1 (Enable RFB manufacturers to reliably calculate the entries required for the digital product passport of redox flow batteries)	EP_PE_1	S

Table 2. User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

¹² For the Policy Expert role, here and below, the requirements are from: Industry sector representative (flow batteries)

Story ID	Design target	Role	Concretely described action	Overarching objective	Falls under broader story (ID)	Priority
EP_DI_4	(n/a - epic)	DI	Use digital twin for product optimization	Improve battery manufacturing processes and products	(n/a - epic)	n/a
US_MLP_DI_3	MLP	DI	Predict battery performance in dependence of design parameter choice	EP_DI_4 (Use digital twin for product optimization)	EP_DI_4	M
US_DSS_DI_1	DSS	DI	Find optimal wrt, performance/costs design parameter sets	EP_DI_4 (Use digital twin for product optimization)	EP_DI_4	M
US_MLP_DI_4	MLP	DI	Predict battery performance for new materials	EP_DI_4 (Use digital twin for product optimization)	EP_DI_4	S

Table 2 User stories grouped by epics (continuation)

Mapping of architecture components to work packages

To ensure the gathered user stories are taken up by the relevant work packages, we provide below a mapping of architecture components to work packages. It is therefore intended those WPs take responsibility to include the relative requirements in their developments.

Architecture component	Component abbreviation	Main responsible WP
(1) Decision support system [incl. DoE+DoS]	DSS	WP5
(2) Knowledge base - central	KBC	WP4
(3) Knowledge base - peripheral	KBP	WP4
(4) Real-time environment [incl. actionable models]	RTE	WP5
(5) Semantic interoperability layer	SIL	WP4
(6) Data and knowledge management software [incl. API]	DKMS	WP4
(7) Machine learning predictors [incl. surrogate models]	MLP	WP5
(8) Physics-based modelling	PBM	WP2
(9) Experimental characterization facilities [incl. ELN]	EXP	WP1
(10) Pilots [incl. sensorics / on-line characterization]	PIL	WP6
(11) Large-data storage	LDS	WP4
(12) DT visualization and human-computer interaction	DTV	WP5

Table 3. List of architecture components, abbreviation and main responsible WP

Appendix D: Competency questions

In this section, we give the competency question and facts (Table 5), tagged using the properties given in Table 4 below (prefix and area). At the end of the section we give example queries, in Table 6, similarly tagged.

Property	Values
Prefix	CQ=Competency Question, EQ=Example Query, FA=Fact
Area(s)	EXP=Experiment, SIM=Simulation, MAN=Manufacturing, DAT=Data , CRO=cross-area

Table 4. Properties and values of tags used for CQs, EQs and facts

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA)	Answer [for questions only]
CQ_CRO_1	What are the main properties of the electrode?	Surface chemical composition, surface area, conductivity, surface hydrophilicity, exchange current rate, diffusional coefficient, tortuosity, porosity, stability of the surface towards modifications
CQ_CRO_2	What are the main properties of the electrolyte?	Composition (salts, solvents), purity, transport properties (viscosity, ionic conductivity), density
CQ_CRO_3	What are the major time scales for process industry? (to classify various types of DTs)	Industrial safety, intermediate, planning
CQ_CRO_4	What are the main components of an RFB?	Bipolar plates, membranes, carbon felt, electrolyte
CQ_CRO_5	What are the variables for optimization (both MCO and ASP)?	Pressure (P) Flow rate (F) Porosity (Ψ) Li diffusion (D_Li) Electronic conductivity (σ) Open-circuit voltage (V_oc) Electrolyte properties (E) Carbon binder properties (C_b) Separator properties (S_p) Intercalation kinetics (K) Li amount (Li_a) Temperature (T) Particle size distribution (P_s) Material properties (M) Concentration profiles (C_p) Diffusion rates (D_r) Viscosity (η) Thermodynamic properties (Th) Transport properties (Tr) Cell design parameters (Cd) Transport parameters (Tp) Geometrical parameters (G) Microstructure parameters (Mp) Material potentials (Mp) Reaction kinetics (Rk)

Table 5. Competency questions and facts

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA)	Answer [for questions only]		
CQ_CRO_6	What are the targets of the optimization (objective function, both in MCO and ASP)?	(Maximize)	Efficiency	(Eff)
		(Maximize)	Lifespan	(L)
		(Maximize)	Capacity	(C)
		(Maximize)	Safety	(S)
CQ_CRO_7	What are the constraints of the (ASP?) optimization?	Pressure (P), $P > P_{max}$ Overpotential (O), $O > O_{max}$ Heat (H), $H > H_{max}$ Thickness (T), $T < T_{min}$ Diffusion rate (D _r), $D_r < D_{min}$ Pressure (P), $P > P_{max}$		
CQ_CRO_8	What are the high-level types of optimization problems that can benefit from logic-based approaches?	Scheduling (e.g., of maintenance); Allocation of resources (e.g., machines/humans for tasks); Compatibility checks (e.g., between materials); Compliance (e.g., of a process with regulation); Process design (e.g., simulation, experiment); Process sequence validation (e.g., that the ordering of sub-processes does not break dependencies)		
CQ_CRO_9	What are the main scales for processes in RFB?	Molecular scale, Fiber scale, Pore scale, Cell scale, Stack scale, Battery system scale, Energy system scale		
FA_CRO_1	For manufacturing and battery variables, a duplication is done: there is a "real" (i.e., measured) and "digital twin" (predicted/simulated) version and they are clearly separated	n/a - fact		
FA_CRO_2	Procedures, protocols, workflows are all processes	n/a - fact		
FA_CRO_3	Materials incompatibilities need to be pointed out (e.g., mixtures that are unsafe)	n/a - fact		
CQ_DAT_1	Is the data(set) complete? ¹³	Yes, No		
CQ_DAT_2	Does the data(set) contain dummy values?	Yes, No		
CQ_DAT_3	What is the mapping between raw data and pre-processed inputs to AI tools?	TBD, cf. CQ_DAT_3.1 for some examples		
CQ_DAT_3.1	How are incomplete raw data records (datasets) pre-processed for AI?	Incomplete dataset is dropped, incomplete dataset is padded with dummy values		
CQ_DAT_4	What types of data quality checks / guarantees are available within BatCAT?	Human assessment, Quality insurance procedures (e.g., regular calibration checks for instance), Repeatability tests with automated treatment		
CQ_DAT_5	What is the average value and error of property X over a certain set (e.g., time window)? (Note: tolerance and other statistics could be added)	n/a - case-specific		

Table 5. Competency questions and facts (continuation)

¹³ That is, complete with respect to some schema or expected data structure.

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA)	Answer [for questions only]
CQ_DAT_6.1	Which (generic) file formats are used in BatCAT?	Comma-separated Values (CSV), Unformatted text (TXT), Unidata's Network Common Data Form Data Model (netCDF), Python script (py), Rich Text Format (RTF), JavaScript Object Notation for Linking Data (JSON-LD), JavaScript Object Notation (JSON), Portable Network Graphics (PNG), Hyper Text Markup Language (HTML)
CQ_EXP_2	What types of documents store the information about purchased materials, as stated by the vendor?	Certificate of analysis (CPI), Material sheet (VANEVO)
CQ_EXP_3	What are the main characterizations needed for LiB/NiB?	Slurry properties, Coating thickness, Active materials potential, Active material granulometry, Active material diffusion, Electrode conductivity, Electrode porosity, Electrode tortuosity, Full cell capacity, Full cell power, Full cell aging
CQ_EXP_3.1	What are the high-level types of characterization needed for RFB?	Electrochemical characterization, Physical characterization (Mechanical?), Fluid (fluidodynamic, rheology) characterization
CQ_EXP_3.2	What are the main characterizations needed for RFB?	Electrolyte viscosity, Electrolyte cyclic voltametry, Felt surface properties, Felt porosity, Felt thickness, Felt conductivity, Felt hydraulic resistance, Membrane thickness, Membrane conductivity, Full cell cycling, Post mortem analysis of aged components
CQ_MAN_1	What are the (variable) parameters of the electrode material synthesis procedure?	TBD
CQ_MAN_2.1	What were the manufacturing process steps to produce the cell?	TBD (cf. CQ_MAN_5.1 and CQ_MAN_5.2)
CQ_MAN_3	What are the main properties of a sensor?	Type/measured variable (temperature, ...), connection type (WiFi/Bluetooth, optical fibre, wired electrical cable)
CQ_MAN_3.1	What are the quantities measured for on-line characterization of LIB?	Temperature, Vibration, Energy consumption, Gas detection, Viscosity, Pressure, single component Vibration, blade Temperature, Porosity, Thickness

Table 5. Competency questions and facts (continuation)

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA)	Answer [for questions only]
CQ_MAN_3.2	What are the sensor types for on-line characterization of LIB?	Thermocouples, Accelerometer + vibration sensor, Power monitoring clip, CO / CO2 sensor, Pressure sensor, Laser profilometer
CQ_MAN_4	What are the main (manufacturing) quantities to monitor?	Energy consumption, Equipment performance, Waste produced (amount), Product quality
CQ_MAN_5.1	What are the main ordered steps in the LIB/NIB manufacturing process?	Mixing, Coating, Drying, Calendering, Cutting, Assembly, Filling, Forming, Degassing
CQ_MAN_5.2	What are the main ordered steps in the RFB manufacturing process?	(Incoming goods inspection), Stack assembly, Stack compression, Stack sealing (glueing), (Stack testing), Tanks: Assembly stacks+Piping+Periphery, (Tanks testing)
CQ_MAN_6.1	What are the LIB/NIB battery (product) design parameters?	Active material choice, Formulation, Particle Size Distribution (PSD), Electrolyte composition, Separator, Size
CQ_MAN_6.2	What are the RFB battery (product) design parameters?	Current density, Ion species concentration, Electrode base material, Volume flow rate, Product dimensions
CQ_MAN_6.3	What are the battery operating conditions?	TBD
CQ_MAN_7.1	What are the control/process parameters of the LIB/NIB manufacturing process?	Solvent choice, Mixing protocol, Coating gap, Coating speed, Pump speed, Drying temperature, Drying speed, Calendering thickness, Electrode geometry, Electrolyte volume, Soak conditions, Formation protocol
CQ_MAN_7.2	What are the control/process parameters of the RFB manufacturing process?	Processing atmosphere, Processing time, Processing temperature, Throughput rate
CQ_MAN_8.1	What are the variables to evaluate the LIB/NIB manufacturing process?	Scrap (rate), Production cost (per unit)
CQ_MAN_8.2	What are the variables to evaluate the RFB manufacturing process?	Production performance, Production cost, Throughput failure rate
CQ_MAN_9.1	What are the LIB/NIB battery product main properties?	Initial performance, Ageing, Safety
CQ_MAN_9.2	What are the RFB battery product main properties?	Efficiency, Capacity, Durability, Round trip efficiency
CQ_MAN_10	What are other general input parameters of the manufacturing process?	Electricity cost, Personnel cost
CQ_MAN_11	How are labels for batches defined (i.e., what parameters of the batch have to be included as part of a label)?	E.g., template of a string in format could be: '%BATCH_NUMBER%_%WEEK%%YEAR%_%BASE_MATERIAL_1%_%BASE_MATERIAL_2%'
FA_MAN_1	A sample belongs to a batch	n/a - fact

Table 5. Competency questions and facts (continuation)

ID	Competency Question (CQ) / Natural language sentence (fact) (FA)	Answer [for questions only]
CQ_SIM_1	What force field was used to obtain the (molecular) simulation results?	n/a - case-specific
CQ_SIM_2	Are these input data compatible (=directly usable) by software X (version V)?	Yes, No
CQ_SIM_3	What are the modelling approaches for LiB?	Atomistic & electronic models (Ab initio DFT Reactive MD Classical MC/MD); Mesoscopic models; Electrode models (4D resolved Phase field); Cell models (P3D, P2D, SP Circuit model)
CQ_SIM_4	What are the modelling approaches for RFB?	Atomistic models (Ab initio DFT Reactive MD Classical MC/MD); Continuum models for flow field (porous media flow), and electrochemistry (Poisson-Nernst-Planck, possibly others)
FA_SIM_1	Surrogate models can be classified by the dimensionality of input and output fed to the neural network (e.g., input can be numbers, geometry/image, a transient; predict a scalar quantity - 0D, local quantity (field), replace an equation - 4D)	n/a - fact

Table 5. Competency questions and facts (continuation)

ID	Example Query (EQ)	Answer
EQ_EXP_1	What is the measured value of the property Z (e.g., porosity) of the electrode material synthesized according to X and Y synthesis parameters?	n/a - EQ, answer will be case specific
EQ_SIM_1	What models/parametrizations of a certain class (e.g., DPD) can be applied to a certain system (e.g., water with vanadium ions)?	n/a - EQ, answer will be case specific

Table 6. Example queries

Appendix E: Characterization techniques and instruments

In this section, we list the main characterization techniques that will be used within BatCAT, and the mapping to the instruments used. For each technique, its high-level type, the battery types it applies to and the quantities evaluated are given as well. The first table is for techniques of electrochemical type, the second one for physicochemical and rheology ones.

This information complements what is given as competency questions in [Appendix D](#) and will also serve as an input for the BatCAT ontology development.

High level characterization type	Characterization technique	Instrument used	Battery type	Quantity evaluated
Electrochemical	Calendar aging	Potentiostat	LIB/NIB, RFB	Full cell aging
Electrochemical	Charge test	Potentiostat	LIB/NIB	Charge capabilities
Electrochemical	Charge test	Potentiostat	RFB	Performance
Electrochemical	Conductivity measurement	Conductivity probe	LIB/NIB	Electrode conductivity
Electrochemical	Cyclic voltametry	Potentiostat	RFB	Electrolyte electrochemical properties
Electrochemical	Cycling	Potentiostat	LIB/NIB, RFB	Full cell aging
Electrochemical	Discharge test	Potentiostat	LIB/NIB	Full cell capacity
Electrochemical	Discharge test	Potentiostat	RFB	Performance
Electrochemical	Duty profile test	Potentiostat	RFB	Round trip efficiency
Electrochemical	EIS test	Potentiostat	LIB/NIB	Impedance
Electrochemical	GITT test	Potentiostat	LIB/NIB	Diffusion coefficient, Active material potentials
Electrochemical	HPPC test	Potentiostat	LIB/NIB	OCV and resistance/Full cell power
Electrochemical	Road profile test	Potentiostat	LIB/NIB	Round trip efficiency

Table 7. Characterization techniques, instruments, evaluated quantities.

High level characterization type	Characterization technique	Instrument used	Battery type	Quantity evaluated
Physicochemical	BET measurement	BET surface area analyzer	RFB	Active surface area
Physicochemical	Conductivity measurement	Electrochemical impedance spectroscopy (EIS).	RFB	Felt conductivity
Physicochemical	Direct measurement	Palmer	RFB	Membrane thickness
Physicochemical	Electrode thickness assessment	Palmer	LIB/NIB	Coating thickness
Physicochemical	Hg porosimetry	Porosimeter	LIB/NIB	Electrode porosity
Physicochemical	Porosimetry	Porosimeter	RFB	Felt porosity
Physicochemical	Raman	Raman	LIB/NIB	Morphology and composition
Physicochemical	Raman	Raman	RFB	Felt surface properties
Physicochemical	SEM	SEM	LIB/NIB	Microscopic geometry/ Active material granulometry/ Electrode tortuosity
Physicochemical	SEM	SEM	RFB	Felt surface properties
Physicochemical	XPS	XPS	LIB/NIB	Morphology and composition
Physicochemical	XPS	XPS	RFB	Felt surface properties
Rheology	Pressure drop measurement	Pressure flow sensor (within single cell test bench)	RFB	Pressure drop

Table 7. Characterization techniques, instruments, evaluated quantities (continuation).